
College Pharmacy Students' Perception of Academic Professors' Online Teaching Performance: An Empirical Perspective from the University of Perpetual Help-Dr. Jose G. Tamayo Medical University

Ace N. Bombaes, MPA¹, Analiza P. Malalay, PhD², & Eduardo Soriano Jr., RPh²

¹University of Perpetual Help System-Pueblo de Panay Campus

²University of Perpetual Help-Dr. Jose G. Tamayo Medical University

Abstract

The study delves on pharmacy students' perception of academic professors' online teaching performance and the factors that influence it. The main research question pertains to identifying factors that significantly influence students' perception of their academic professors at the University of Perpetual Help-Dr. Jose G. Tamayo Medical University. Survey questionnaire was utilized to elicit information from 125 respondents with the help of SPSS v17 as the analyzing tool. The findings show that respondents regarded all these factors neutral which means that most of them were less inclined to express their actual opinion, thus giving the researchers an impression based on the gathered data that they were not satisfied with the way how teaching practices were executed and shown online. Therefore, the researchers adopted a paradigm on reflective teaching strategies, a six-step process which can help them as pedagogical practitioners.

Keywords: student perception, attitude, teaching method, teaching performance, online classroom effectiveness, reflective teaching

** Corresponding author: Ace N. Bombaes, MPA, University of Perpetual Help-Pueblo de Panay, e-mail: bombaes_21@yahoo.com

Introduction

COVID-19 pandemic has brought many challenges and has affected many sectors including the education sector. During this period, students along with their teachers have been hindered from going to school and attending their face-to-face classes. As a result, online teaching and learning has been heavily used in order to adapt to the new normal.

Teachers or professors play a vital role in terms of educating students. They are crucial fundamental variables in the teaching and learning (Sultan, S. et al., 2014). As expected, teacher must be competent in terms of her knowledge about the subject and the way how she effectively delivers it to her students.

The study aims to find out and evaluate students' perception of their academic professors' online teaching performance and the factors that affect students' perception. It wishes to provide a paradigm or steps on reflective teaching strategies that one can put into practice in order to plan a strong foundation since the success of every student towards achieving his/her goals start from having a strong foundation of knowledge and practical skills brought by their teachers. Although the faculty of the College of Pharmacy had already been observed by their dean before the study was conducted, there has not been a formal evaluation or study conducted by the department that would explore students' perception and the factors that influence it. Therefore, there is a need to explore, assess and evaluate the said perception and the factors. The results of

this study would draw a reference as to what and how proper interventions would be conducted in order to bridge the gap towards enriching academic professors' online teaching performance especially in the new normal.

Research Objectives

The objectives of the study are to measure and explore students' perception of their academic professors' online teaching performance and provide reflective ways of teaching that can help the teaching force of the College of Pharmacy enhance, enrich and improve their pedagogical strategies that can bridge the gap towards achieving highly effective and satisfying teaching and learning in the new normal.

Literature Review

The study clearly defines the factors that contribute to students' perception of their academic professors such as teacher's attitude (Mazana et al., 2018), strategy and method of teaching (Shahida Sajjad, n.d.), teacher's mastery (Fakeye, 2012), teacher's support (Xiao-xianLiu et.al 2021) classroom effectiveness (Ni, 2013) can potentially influence students' perception on teachers' online teaching performance. This paper examines the key factors in order to provide information and feedback which in turn should enable them to take some necessary actions to enhance their teaching performance in the future. These key factors pertain to teachers' characteristics and professional qualities. Students' views and feedback offer significant insights as to how teachers could greatly engage students in the act of acquiring useful information, as to how they might foster effective ways of teaching, and as to how they might make the learning process more collaborative, interactive, interesting and enjoyable for students especially in the new normal where online classes are heavily used by many professionals, students and learning institutions like the University of Perpetual Help System Campuses.

Teacher is the heart of a class and without her class will be colorless and considered as the most important element in the development of an education programs. Her influence plays a significant role in students' learning outcomes and learning habits. Her teaching can have significant impacts on students' academic success (Odiri, 2011). In order to carry out the teaching task well, teacher should be well-equipped with characteristics and professional qualities and should be guided with principles of teaching which can have a huge impact on students' academic success.

1.1 Perception on Teacher's Attitude

Teacher sets standards by establishing interpersonal relationship with her students which is seen and perceived by students. This relationship can be felt by many especially when she shows that she cares and values every student in her class. According to John Locke as cited by Androne (2014), teacher plays a significant role in shaping her pupils whom she has to transform into a model of behavior, training him step to face the demands of real life to the best of abilities. According to Locke's beliefs, a teacher is responsible for raising a child's moral profile, preparing him for the demands of social life, and developing humane discipline. A teacher must play an active, effective, and facilitating role in changing students into healthy competitors and qualified individuals who possess the values and competencies required for success in life.

1.2 Perception on Teaching Method

According to Teo & Noyes (2011), teaching skills identified include the ability to adapt content of the training, level of depth and teaching method according to the needs of any particular group. Thorough comprehension of students' context (level of knowledge, prior experience and insight in the curriculum) is considered helpful. The success of teaching and learning process also depends on how effective the teaching method is thus defining the possible learning outcomes based on students perceived and received it. It is said that a teaching method can help students to fully understand the lessons thus eliminating any barriers to effective teaching and learning.

1.3 Perception on Classroom Effectiveness

Effective teaching can be defined as meeting the target learning outcomes and producing positive outputs based on the set learning goals and objectives of the program. It reflects on the teacher's performance on how she teaches the subject matter with mastery and effective way of teaching it. According to Ibrahim (2014), the effectiveness of teacher depends on some factors like attitude towards students, the relationship with students, and the teaching method used in class. Furthermore, students find teacher effective when she applies a much easier, better, more rewarding and more appropriate method of teaching that majority of her students can easily grasp the concept and apply this learned concept

1.4 Perception on Teacher's Mastery

The master of the subject matter is the foundation upon which the education is based. Teacher should be able to establish herself with different subjects which is essential for the preparation for the teacher's professional preparation (Kamamia et al., 2014). Teacher's subject mastery is considered one of the predictors of students' achievement (Fakeye, 2012). teachers' competence in subject matter does actually influence students' interest (Obot, 2014).

1.5 Perception on Teacher's Support

According to (Lei et al., 2018), there is a strong relationship between teacher support and students' academic emotions. Teachers who value their students by caring for them are perceived as emotionally supportive. By helping students to better understand the lesson and by guiding them towards achieving their goals are perceived as supportive (Federici et al., 2016). These reasonable assumptions give emphasis on the function that teacher plays towards student's academic and emotional development.

Conceptual Framework of the Study

The following (Figure 1) conceptual framework of this study which adopted from (Raja, 2017). This shows the design of students' perception of academic professors' online teaching performance practices. Professors' online teaching performance is treated as a dependent variable whereas students' perception regarding professors' attitude, teaching method, classroom effectiveness, mastery, and support as independent variables.

Figure 1 Conceptual Framework

The diagrammatic view presents that the dependent variable is fixed in the middle while independent variables present the effect on the dependent variable with pointing arrows.

Methodology

The study is a descriptive research of the survey method. Questionnaire was utilized to elicit information from students' perception of their academic professors as regards online teaching. The sample for the study was composed of 125 college students who were randomly selected from the College of Pharmacy in the study. Statistical analyses were performed using SPSS v17.0.

Data Analysis Results

The students' perception on academic professor's online teaching performance questionnaire is composed of 23 questions and each response scale ranges from strongly agree to strongly disagree. Internal consistency of the questionnaire is assessed using Cronbach's alpha. Table 1 shows the reliability of each instrument.

Findings

The students' perception on academic professor's online teaching performance questionnaire is composed of 23 questions and each response scale ranges from strongly agree to strongly disagree. Internal consistency of the questionnaire is assessed using Cronbach's alpha. Table 1 shows the reliability of each instrument.

Table 1

Questionnaire's Reliability

Factors	N of Items	Cronbach's Alpha	Cronbach's Alpha Based on Standardized Items
Teacher's Attitude	5	0.955	0.957
Teacher's Method	4	0.965	0.966
Classroom Effectiveness	5	0.975	0.975
Teacher's Mastery	5	0.948	0.949
Teacher's Support	3	0.951	0.952
Teacher's Online Performance	5	0.883	0.983

Table 1 demonstrates the factors that influence students' perception of their academic professors' online teaching performance and the overall consistency of the factors. This also shows that each factor and academic professor's online teaching performance are highly reliable, thus indicating the accuracy and consistency of the constructs.

Table 2: Pearson Correlation

Factors	Item	Total
Teacher's Attitude	Q1	.920*
	Q2	.936**
	Q3	.902**
	Q4	.945**
	Q5	.916**
	Total	1

Teacher's Method	Q1	.945**
	Q2	.971**
	Q3	.959**
	Q4	.935**
	Total	1
Online Classroom Effectiveness	Q1	.964**
	Q2	.948**
	Q3	.951**
	Q4	.961**
	Q5	.939**
	Total	1
Teacher's Mastery	Q1	.926**
	Q2	.914**
	Q3	.961**
	Q4	.848**
	Q5	.848**
	Total	1
Teacher's Support	Q1	.940**
	Q2	.965**
	Q3	.954**
	Total	1

Table 2 shows the correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed). The results indicate that these factors influence students' perception of their academic professors' online teaching performance which implies that all these factors can affect students as to how they regard their academic professors' online teaching performance. Moreover, this perception is associated with how class and other pedagogical strategies and practices are shown and executed online.

Table 3: Interval

Interval	Interpretation
1.01 – 1.80	Strongly Agree
1.81 – 2.60	Agree
2.61 – 3.40	Neutral
3.41 – 4.20	Disagree
4.21 – 5.00	Strongly Disagree

Table 3 shows the Mean of the students' responses of their perceptions towards their Academic Professors' online teaching performance is 2.6787 which means that it is neutral. It would mean that most of the students were not satisfied with the way their academic professors perform and teach online. This also shows that students were less inclined to express their actual opinion on this regard.

Discussions

With great effort drive from both private and public sectors to continue giving quality education to students through online and distance education, the University of Perpetual System-JONELTA Campuses including the Laguna Campus as its main campus have shifted to online platforms to catch up with the current situation caused by COVID-19 pandemic. The findings revealed that that professors' attitude, professors' method,

online classroom effectiveness, professor’s mastery, and professor’s support were neutral. Therefore, there is a need to reflect on all these factors that can influence students’ perception of their professors’ online teaching performance. All these factors should be considered in undertaking an online class which can determine the effectiveness of professors’ online teaching performance and assure the positive influence of it on students’ learning progress in the midst of this pandemic where face-to-face class has been quite impossible to conduct.

Hence this study provides an action plan that can be used for increasing, improving, and showing favorable outcomes as regards these factors such as professors’ attitude, teaching method, online classroom management, mastery of the subject matter, and support.

Limitation and future research

Recommendation

Reflection-in-action

There are multiple ways in seeking out positive changes in teaching practices that enable professors to reflect on and improve performance in class. Being adaptable is the key. It is believed that professors should also develop a strong sense of responsibility. They should refer to technical rationality in which they examine their practice after class reflection-in-action which the professors look back on their action and reflect on it; reflection-for-action which is proactive in nature and lastly action research which is an important part of reflective thinking. Moreover, the researchers want to give more emphasis on the importance of positive attitude as it is the key for engaging in a reflective teaching practice (Shakouri, 2016).

Enabling Change

Figure 2: Bombaes’ Paradigm on Reflective Teaching Strategies

The researchers believe that professors should be more adaptive to change since it is inevitable and everyone should get closer to change especially in the new normal. Professors should reflect on the factors such as attitude, teaching method, online classroom management, mastery of the subject matter, and support. They should think of some possible ways in order to modify, enhance, and enrich their teaching pedagogies, methods, and goals, as well as their attitude to be more welcoming, supportive and attentive to students’ academic and emotional needs. Professors should also develop a strong sense of efficacy which is a necessary ingredient to positively influence students towards learning (Nosratinia & Moradi, 2017). The importance of a strong commitment to quality education allows us to constantly seek ways to improve and enrich ourselves as pedagogical practitioners (Bombaes A. et.al. 2021).

References

- [1] Androne, M. (2014). Notes on John Locke's Views on Education. *Procedia - Social and Behavioral Sciences*, 137, 74–79. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.sbspro.2014.05.255>
- [2] Fakeye, D. O. (2012). *Teachers' Qualification and Subject Mastery as Predictors of Achievement in English Language in Ibarapapa Division of Oyo State*. 12(3), 0–6.
- [3] Federici, R. A., Caspersen, J., & Wendelborg, C. (2016). Students' Perceptions of Teacher Support, Numeracy, and Assessment for Learning: Relations with Motivational Responses and Mastery Experiences. *International Education Studies*, 9(10), 1. <https://doi.org/10.5539/ies.v9n10p1>
- [4] Ibrahim, A.-W. (2014). The Students' Perception of Teachers' Classroom Effectiveness on Their Self-Concepts in Lagos Metropolis. *Journal of Teaching and Teacher Education*, 2(2), 133–141. <https://doi.org/10.12785/jtte/020209>
- [5] Kamamia, L. N., Ngugi, N. T., & Thinguri, R. W. (2014). To Establish the Extent to Which the Subject Mastery Enhances Quality Teaching to Student-Teachers During Teaching Practice. *International Journal of Education and Research*, 2(7), 641–648. <https://ijern.com/journal/July-2014/51.pdf>
- [6] Lei, H., Cui, Y., & Chiu, M. M. (2018). The relationship between teacher support and students' academic emotions: A meta-analysis. *Frontiers in Psychology*, 8(JAN), 1–12.
- [7] Mazana, M. Y., Montero, C. S., & Casmir, R. O. (2018). Investigating Students' Attitude towards Learning Mathematics. *International Electronic Journal of Mathematics Education*, 14(1), 207–231. <https://doi.org/10.29333/iejme/3997>
- [8] Ni, A. Y. (2013). Comparing the Effectiveness of Classroom and Online Learning: Teaching Research Methods. *Journal of Public Affairs Education*, 19(2), 199–215. <https://doi.org/10.1080/15236803.2013.12001730>
- [9] Nosratinia, M., & Moradi, Z. (2017). *EFL Teachers' Reflective Teaching, Use of Motivational Strategies, and Their Sense of Efficacy*. 8(2), 431–439.
- [10] Obot, I. M. (2014). Influence of teacher's competence in subject matter on students' interest in the learning of social studies education in Akwa Ibom. *International Journal of Teaching and Education*, 2(3), 137–154.
- [11] Odiri, O. E. (2011). THE INFLUENCE OF TEACHERS' ATTITUDE ON STUDENTS' LEARNING OF MATHEMATICS IN NIGERIAN SECONDARY SCHOOLS Onoshakpokaiye E. Odiri. *Journal of Research in Education and Society*, 2(1), 15–21. [file:///C:/Users/acer/Desktop/The Influence of Teachers Attitude on Students Learning of Mathematics in Nigerian Secondary Schools.pdf](file:///C:/Users/acer/Desktop/The%20Influence%20of%20Teachers%20Attitude%20on%20Students%20Learning%20of%20Mathematics%20in%20Nigerian%20Secondary%20Schools.pdf)
- [12] Raja, F. (2017). Journal of Education and Educational Development. *Journal of Education and Educational Development*, 4(1), 94–110.
- [13] Shahida Sajjad. (n.d.). *Effective Teaching Methods at Higher*. 1–16.
- [14] Shakouri, N. (2016). *Critical Thinking in Higher Education: A Pedagogical Look*. July 2012. <https://doi.org/10.4304/tpls.2.7.1370-1375>
- [15] Sultan, S., & Shafi, M. (2014). Impact of Perceived Teachers' Competence on Students' Performance: Evidence for Mediating/ Moderating Role of Class Environment. *I-Manager's Journal on Educational Psychology*, 8(1), 10–18. <https://doi.org/10.26634/jpsy.8.1.2764>
- [16] Teo, T., & Noyes, J. (2011). An assessment of the influence of perceived enjoyment and attitude on the intention to use technology among pre-service teachers: A structural equation modeling approach. *Computers and Education*, 57(2), 1645–1653. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.compedu.2011.03.002>